

ISic3040

I.Sicily inscription 3040

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334297

1. [I]έρωνος.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645394

PHI 334297

Bibliography

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Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1991. Meligunìs Lipára V. Scavi nella necropoli
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